

2-Aminothiazole Derivatives. Part II

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Phenyl-2-amino-5-thiazolyl sulphides and sulphones, having various substituents in the phenyl ring, have been prepared with a view to studying their antibacterial properties. 2-Acetamido-5-bromothiazole has been condensed with potassium salt of various thiophenols in presence of propylene glycol to furnish phenyl-2-acetamido-5-thiazolyl sulphides, which have been further oxidised to the corresponding sulphones by hydrogen peroxide in glacial acetic acid. The acetamido-sulphides and sulphones have been hydrolysed by EtOH-HCl to the corresponding amino-sulphides and -sulphones. Some of these compounds have been found to be bacteriostatic *in vitro* tests against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*.

p p'-Diaminodiphenyl sulphone (DADS) is well known for its use as a drug of choice in the treatment of leprosy. It gives rise occasionally, however, to toxic side effects. In order to reduce toxicity and retain activity of DADS, Roblin *et al.*¹ and Bambas² substituted one of the phenyl nuclei of DADS by a heterocyclic nucleus and found them relatively less toxic and more effective in the treatment of leprosy.

In view of the above considerations it was thought worthwhile to make further alterations in phenyl part of the promizole structure and thereby study their antibacterial properties. At present, halogen, methyl, and alkoxy, substituents have been introduced into the phenyl ring to obtain phenyl-2-amino-5-thiazolyl sulphones of the type:

(R=R₁=H, Cl, Br, Me or OM₃ and R₂=H, Cl, Br, M₃, OM₃, OEt, OPrⁿ, and OBuⁿ)

The synthesis of phenyl-2-amino-5-thiazolyl sulphones having hydroxy and chloro substituents will be reported elsewhere.

Phenyl-2-amino-5-thiazolyl sulphides, isosteric with 4-aminodiphenyl sulphides, are also expected to show considerable antibacterial activity *in vitro* tests because Freedlander and French³ have found 4-aminophenyl-4-halophenyl sulphides to be strongly bacteriostatic *in vitro* tests against *tubercle bacilli*.

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1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 1930.

2. *Ibid.*, 1945, **67**, 671.

3. *Proc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1946, **63**, 361.

For the preparation of phenyl-2-acetamido-5-thiazolylsulphides, nucleophilic replacement of bromine in 2-acetamido-5-bromothiazole using alkali salt of a thiophenol seemed to be very convenient. But the condensation did not proceed in presence of ethanol even after the reaction mixture was refluxed for a number of hours. The condensation, however, was brought about successfully when a mixture of equimolecular quantities of reactants was heated at 130-35° in presence of propylene glycol for about 4 hours. Yields of the sulphides were as high as 80%.

These acetamido sulphides were oxidised to acetamido sulphones by hydrogen peroxide in glacial acetic acid. The authenticity of the sulphones was proved by preparing one member of the series by an unambiguous method. For example, 2,4-dichlorophenyl-2-acetamido-5-thiazolyl sulphone (m.p. 294°), obtained by condensing 2-acetamido-5-bromothiazole with sodium 2,4-dichlorobenzenesulphinate in propylene glycol, showed no depression in m.p. on admixture with the sample (m.p. 292°) prepared by oxidation of 2,4-dichlorophenyl 2-acetamido-5-thiazolyl sulphide.

Phenyl-2-amino-5-thiazolyl sulphides and sulphones were prepared by hydrolysing the corresponding acetamido sulphides and sulphones with ethanolic HCl.

Some of the amino sulphides and sulphones are active *in vitro* tests against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* and the results of the testing will be published elsewhere.

EXPERIMENTAL

Various thiophenols, required in the present work, were prepared by the Leuckart reaction from the corresponding anilines, where as 3-bromo-4-methoxythiophenol and 3-bromo-6-methoxythiophenol were prepared by reduction of the corresponding benzene-sulphonyl chlorides. 2-Acetamido-5-bromothiazole was prepared according to the method of Baker and Buismans.

Phenyl-2-acetamido-5-thiazolyl Sulphides and Sulphones (General Method).—A mixture of 2-acetamido-5-bromothiazole (0.02M), potassium salt of a thiophenol (0.02M), and freshly distilled propylene glycol (15-20 ml) was heated at 130-40° for about 4 hours. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into water and the crude residue macerated with 10% NaOH to dissolve any unchanged thiophenol and 2-acetamido-5-bromothiazole. It was filtered, washed with water, and dried. Since some of the product became deacetylated during condensation, the crude sulphide was heated with acetic anhydride (10 ml) for 15 minutes and worked up in the usual way. To a solution of a sulphide (0.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid was added 30% H₂O₂ (2 ml) and the mixture kept for 60 hours with intermittent addition of H₂O₂ (0.5 ml) at an interval of 20 hours. At the end of oxidation period a crystalline mass separated. In case where no solid separated, the solution was diluted to precipitate the sulphone. All sulphides and sulphones were crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colorless needles. Various acetamido sulphides and sulphones are reported in Table I.

4. Hoggarth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 110.

5. *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1944, 63, 226.

TABLE I

Phenyl-2-acetamido-5-thiazolyl Sulphides and Sulphones.

S.No.	Substituents in phenyl ring.	Yield.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	..	80%	226-27 ^a	N : 11.25%	11.20%
	Sulphone	..	273-74	S : 25.76	25.61
2.	2-Bromo-4-methyl	78	202-03	N : 9.99	9.93
	Sulphone	..	261-62	S : 22.53	22.70
3.	2-Methyl-4-bromo	80	204-05	N : 8.00	8.16
	Sulphone	..	290-91	S : 18.52	18.66
4.	3-Chloro-4-bromo	75	195-96	N : 7.56	7.47
	Sulphone	..	262-63	S : 17.22	17.07
5.	3-Bromo-4-methoxy	78	248-49	N : 8.30	8.16
	Sulphone	..	286-87	S : 18.55	18.66
6.	3-Bromo-6-methoxy	70	210-11	N : 7.39	7.47
	Sulphone	..	237-38	S : 17.28	17.07
7.	2,5-Dichloro-4-ethoxy	60	212-13	N : 7.56	7.70
	Sulphone	..	280 (decomp.)	S : 17.54	17.61
8.	3-Chloro-4-propoxy ^a	72	145-46	N : 7.19	7.08
	Sulphone	..	216-17	S : 15.99	16.18
9.	2-Chloro-4-butoxy ^a	70	164-65	N : 7.72	7.90
	Sulphone	..	214-15	S : 17.96	17.82
10.	2,3-Dichloro	80	229-30	N : 7.01	7.16
	Sulphone	..	265-66	S : 16.54	16.37
11.	2,4-Dichloro	70	209-10	N : 7.68	7.80
	Sulphone	..	292-93	S : 17.95	17.82
12.	2,5-Dichloro	76	222-24	N : 7.25	7.16
	Sulphone	..	245-46	S : 16.46	16.37
				N : 7.58	7.71
				Cl : 19.48	19.56
				N : 7.21	7.09
				Cl : 18.05	17.98
				N : 8.24	8.18
				S : 18.50	18.69
				N : 7.39	7.48
				S : 17.23	17.09
				N : 7.67	7.86
				S : 17.78	17.98
				N : 7.35	7.20
				S : 16.61	16.47
				N : 8.85	8.78
				Cl : 22.09	22.26
				N : 8.11	7.98
				Cl : 20.48	20.23
				N : 8.67	8.7
				Cl : 22.35	22.26
				N : 8.06	7.98
				Cl : 20.02	20.23
				N : 8.59	8.78
				Cl : 22.44	22.26
				N : 7.79	7.98
				Cl : 20.38	20.23

TABLE II (contd.)

S.No.	Substituents in phenyl ring.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
7.	2,5-Dichloro-4-ethoxy	152-53°	N : 8.69 Cl : 22.45	8.72 22.12
	Hydrochloride	197-98	Equiv. : 355	357.5
	Sulphone	249-50	N : 8.11 Cl : 20.34	7.03 20.11
8.	3-Chloro-4-propoxy ^a	110-11	N : 9.22 S : 21.47	9.32 21.29
	Hydrochloride	80-90	Equiv. : 334	337
	Sulphone	191-92	N : 8.53 S : 19.14	8.42 19.25
9.	2-Chloro-4-butoxy ^b	80-87	N : 8.81 S : 20.55	8.02 20.38
	Hydrochloride	82-83	Equiv. : 350	351
	Sulphone	151-52	N : 7.93 S : 18.06	8.08 18.47
10.	2,3-Dichloro	175-76	N : 10.24 Cl : 25.75	10.11 25.64
	Hydrochloride	211-12	Equiv. : 315	313.5
	Sulphone	219-20	N : 9.14 Cl : 23.03	9.06 22.08
11.	2,4-Dichloro	166-67	N : 10.15 Cl : 25.42	10.11 25.64
	Hydrochloride	198-99	Equiv. : 310	313.5
	Sulphone	186-87	N : 8.94 Cl : 22.77	9.06 22.98
12.	2,5-Dichloro	82-83	N : 9.06 Cl : 25.54	10.11 25.64
	Hydrochloride	181-82	Equiv. : 319	313.5
	Sulphone	227-28	N : 8.94 Cl : 22.73	9.06 22.98

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